

Kinetics and mechanism of osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of L-arginine by hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium

Garapati Sridevi, Nowduri Annapurna and Parvataneni Vani*

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-500 003,
Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : vani_chem@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : The osmium(VIII) catalysed reaction between L-arginine and hexacyanoferrate(III) (HCF(III)) in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry of 1 : 2 with zero order dependence on [HCF(III)]. The reaction is first order with respect to [catalyst], [alkali] and fractional order with respect to [substrate]. No effect of added product was observed.

Keywords : Oxidation of L-arginine, hexacyanoferrate(III), osmium(VIII).

Introduction

Amino acids not only act as building blocks of proteins but also play a significant role in metabolism. Arginine, an essential amino acid, is most important to life, especially to the growth of children. It also finds applications in medicine and pharmaceuticals. Literature survey reveals that kinetic studies on the oxidation of L-arginine using oxidants like chloramine-T^{1,2}, bromamine-T³, hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴, alkaline permanganate⁵, diperiodato nickelate(IV) (DPN)⁶, *N*-bromosuccinimide⁷, Mn^{III}^{8,9}, quinquivalent vanadium^{10,11}, Ru^{III} catalysed alkaline permanganate¹², *N*-chloronicotinamide¹³ and *N*-chlorosaccharin¹⁴ were reported earlier. Osmium(VIII) acts as a catalyst in several redox reactions in alkaline solution. The mechanism of the catalysis is quite complicated due to the formation of different intermediate complexes, free radicals and different oxidation states of osmium.

The uncatalysed oxidation of arginine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) (HCF(III))⁴ was studied at higher temperatures in the range 318–338 K. Since there is no direct reaction between arginine and HCF(III) at 303 K and since osmium(VIII) was found to catalyse the reaction considerably, we have undertaken a detailed kinetic and mechanistic study of the title reaction in 0.4 mol dm⁻³ alkaline medium.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Known amounts of L-arginine were allowed to react completely with a known excess of HCF(III) in presence of osmium(VIII) at 30°C in 0.4 mol dm⁻³ NaOH at an ionic strength of 0.5 mol dm⁻³. The remaining HCF(III) was then analyzed spectrophotometrically. As per these results the stoichiometry was found to correspond to the equation,

where, R = NH₂-C-NH⁻(CH₂)₃-

The test for free radicals was carried out by taking L-arginine, NaOH, Os^{VIII} in a thumberg tube and acrylonitrile and HCF(III) in a bent tube. After evacuating the system the solutions were mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside and even after 24 h no precipitate was observed, indicating the absence of free radicals.

The main oxidation product was identified as aldehyde. It was, confirmed by adding 2,4-DNP to the product solution. Similarly, ammonia is identified by Nessler's reagent.

Effect of ionic strength :

The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the concentration of LiClO_4 from 0.5–1.7 mol dm^{-3} . The pseudo-zero order rate constants obtained from absorbance versus time plots showed that increase in ionic strength (μ) slightly increases the rate of the reaction (Table 1).

Effect of [product] :

The effect of added product on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying the concentration of hexacyanoferrate(II) (HCF(II)) from 2.0–7.0 $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} by keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. The pseudo-zero order rate constants thus obtained were found to remain practically constant indicating that HCF(II) did not have any effect on the rate of the reaction.

Table 1. Effect of $[\text{HCF(III)}]$, $[\text{Arg}]$, $[\text{OH}^-]$ and ionic strength, μ , on the pseudo-zero order rate constant (k_0), at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

$[\text{HCF(III)}] \times 10^4$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{Arg}] \times 10^2$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] \times 10^6$ (mol dm^{-3})	$[\text{OH}^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	μ (mol dm^{-3})	$k_0 \times 10^6$ ($\text{mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
2.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.33
3.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.29
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.50
5.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.33
6.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.20
7.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.15
4.0	0.5	4.0	0.4	0.5	2.30
4.0	0.7	4.0	0.4	0.5	2.93
4.0	1.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	3.16
4.0	1.2	4.0	0.4	0.5	3.46
4.0	1.5	4.0	0.4	0.5	3.96
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.50
4.0	3.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.95
4.0	4.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	5.38
4.0	5.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	5.56
4.0	2.0	2.0	0.4	0.5	2.46
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.46
4.0	2.0	6.0	0.4	0.5	6.50
4.0	2.0	8.0	0.4	0.5	8.43
4.0	2.0	10.0	0.4	0.5	10.9
4.0	2.0	12.0	0.4	0.5	13.5
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.2	0.8	2.46
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.3	0.8	3.28
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.8	4.50
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.5	0.8	5.59
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.6	0.8	6.72
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.7	0.8	7.68
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.5	4.50
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	0.7	5.15
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.0	5.38
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.2	5.75
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.5	6.02
4.0	2.0	4.0	0.4	1.7	7.00

Effect of [substrate] :

In order to find the effect of [arginine] on the rate of the reaction, kinetic runs were carried out by varying the [arginine] at three different temperatures (25, 30 and 35 °C) in the range of $0.5-5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping the concentration of all other species constant in the reaction mixture. The pseudo-zero order rate constants were found to increase with increase in the concentration of arginine and the plot of $\log k_0$ versus $\log [\text{arginine}]$ (Fig. 1) was found to be linear with a slope of 0.5 at 30°C. Further, the plots of $1/k_0$ versus $1/[\text{arginine}]$ were found to be straight lines with positive intercepts on the rate axes indicating that the reaction obeys Michaelis-Menten behaviour.

Effect of [osmium(VIII)] :

The catalyst, [osmium(VIII)] was varied in the range

$2.0-12.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping the concentration of all other reactants constant. When the pseudo-zero order rate constants obtained from the absorbance versus time plots were plotted against [osmium(VIII)], a straight line passing through origin is obtained indicating the order with respect to [osmium(VIII)] to be unity.

Effect of [alkali] :

The effect of alkali on the rate of the reaction was carried out by keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant and varying the $[\text{OH}^-]$ with NaOH by keeping a constant ionic strength of 0.8 mol dm^{-3} at 30 °C. The pseudo-zero order rate constants were found to increase with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$.

The protonation-deprotonation equilibria of L-arginine was shown in Fig. 2. Arginine possess three different

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_0$ versus $\log [\text{arginine}]$.

Fig. 2. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of L-arginine.

pK_a values. One of them corresponding to the carboxylic group ($pK_1 = 2.17$), and the other two for amino ($pK_2 = 9.04$) and guanidinium groups ($pK_3 = 12.48$).

Under the present experimental conditions, at a $[OH^-]$ of 0.4 mol dm^{-3} arginine exists in the form of anionic species, $Arg^-(IV)$ to the extent of 98.5% and as neutral species, $Arg_2(III)$ to the extent of 1.5%. $HCF(III)$ is a low spin octahedral complex.

Osmium(VIII) is known to form different complexes with OH^- and species such as OsO_4 , $[OsO_4(OH)(H_2O)]^-$, $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}$ and $[OsO_5(OH)]^{3-}$ coexist in fast equilibrium with each other in basic medium¹⁶.

When the osmium tetroxide is dissolved in strong alkali, the species, $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2+}$ exists according to the equilibrium^{17,18}.

where $K = 24 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ at 308 K and $\mu = 1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ^{19,20}. Since the present reaction medium is strongly basic, the active form of osmium(VIII) can be presumed to be $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}$. In the present study as the rate of the reaction is fractional order dependent on [arginine] it is involved in complexation with $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}$. Recently Nandibewoor *et al.* also proposed complexation between the catalyst and substrate in the osmium(VIII) catalysed oxidation of sulfanilic acid by $HCF(III)$ in alkaline medium²¹. But since the order with respect to $[HCF(III)]$ is zero, its involvement in the rate-determining step is ruled out. Based on these arguments, the following mechanism is proposed.

$$\frac{-d[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}}{dt} = k[C][OH^-] \quad (4)$$

$$= kK_1[Arg^-]_e[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}]_e [OH^-] \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Since } [Os^{VIII}]_t = [OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}]_e + [C]_e$$

$$\therefore [OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}]_e = \frac{[Os^{VIII}]_t}{1 + K_1[Arg^-]_e} \quad (6)$$

Now, substituting $[OsO_4(OH)_2]^{2-}]_e$ from eq. (6) in eq. (5) leads to

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK_1[Arg^-]_e[OH^-][Os^{VIII}]_t}{1 + K_1[Arg^-]_e} \quad (7)$$

where, $[Arg^-]_e = [Arg]_t$, the above equation may be written as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK_1[Arg]_t[OH^-][Os^{VIII}]_t}{1 + K_1[Arg]_t} \quad (8)$$

This rate equation explains first order dependence each on [osmium(VIII)] and $[OH^-]$ zero order on $[HCF(III)]$ and fractional order with respect to [arginine].

Further, the rate constants of the rate-determining step, k and equilibrium constants, K_1 were determined from the plots of $1/k_o$ versus $1/[arginine]$ at 25, 30 and 35 °C and were presented in Table 2. The activation parameters of the rate-determining step E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were computed using linear least squares method and were found to be $8.58 \pm 2.65 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-225.60 \pm 7.90 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively.

Table 2. Rate constants of rate-determining step

Temp. (K)	k (s^{-1})	K_1 (mol dm^{-3})
303	3.38	10.96
308	4.03	11.53
313	5.00	20.00

Further the direct reaction between arginine and Os^{VIII} [in the order of $10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$] was carried out under experimental conditions employed and it was found to be instantaneous.

The following arguments are in support of the proposed intimate mechanism.

Fig. 3. Plot of $1/k_0$ versus $1/[\text{Arg}]$ at three different temperatures.

Intimate mechanism

(i) It is proposed that a complex is formed between arginine and $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. It is quite appropriate to propose a dissociative step with expulsion of OH^- , one of the ligands and the subsequent attack by arginine on the five coordinated intermediate. However for the first order dependence on $[\text{OH}^-]$ squarely negates such proposal. Hence it is believed that the intermediate complex formed is in a transition state with partial bond formation with the incoming ligand, arginine and partial labilisation of the bond with the outgoing ligand and is in equilibrium with the reactants.

(ii) The intermediate in the presence of $[\text{OH}^-]$ undergoes a quick redox decomposition with Os^{VIII} resulting in to Os^{VI} and the amino acid undergoes decarboxylation and deamination.

(iii) Subsequently Os^{VI} is oxidized by HCF(III) in a fast reaction.

Experimental

The standard solution of L-arginine was prepared by using double distilled water. The other chemicals used were HCF(III), sodium hydroxide, osmium(VIII) and LiClO_4 . All chemicals used were of AR grade. A 0.01 mol dm^{-3} solution of osmium(VIII) was prepared in 0.25 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide from osmium tetroxide (Johnson Mathey, London). Its strength was determined by taking aliquot volume of the solution into 0.5 mol dm^{-3} hydrochloric acid adding 10 ml of 10% KI and titrating the liberated iodine with sodium thiosulphate using starch as indicator¹⁵. Solution of desired concentration is prepared from this stock by suitable dilution.

The reaction was carried out in thermostatic water bath at a constant temperature with an accuracy of $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The reaction was initiated by mixing a calculated amount of HCF(III) to a mixture of L-arginine, sodium hydroxide, osmium(VIII) and lithium perchlorate at a constant temperature of $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of HCF(III) at 420 nm using Milton Roy 1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells.

The temperature is kept constant using a SISKIN JULABO V constant temperature liquid circulatory bath. The test for free radicals was carried out by taking L-arginine, NaOH , Os^{VIII} in a thumberg tube and acrylonitrile and HCF(III) in a bent tube. After evacuating the

system the solutions were mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside and even after 24 h no precipitate was observed, indicating the absence of free radicals.

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